

INFLUENCE OF PLY WAVINESS ON RESIDUAL STRENGTH AND FATIGUE DEGRADATION OF COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADES

M. Draskovic^{1,*}, U.I.K. Galappathithi², A.K. Pickett¹, M. Capellaro¹, P. Middendorf¹

Institute of Aircraft Design, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany,

² School of Engineering and Built Environment, Glasgow Caledonian University, Glasgow, UK

* Corresponding author (milos.draskovic@ifb.uni-stuttgart.de)

Keywords: *fatigue life, residual strength, ply waviness*

1 Introduction

Several dramatic failures of utility-scale wind turbine rotor blades have occurred in the industry news during the past few years. Amongst these a major retrofit program has been necessary to resolve blade cracking issues which was estimated to cost \$25 million [1]. It has also been reported in the UK that 1500 accidents have occurred during the period 2006-2011, and that many of these were due to blade failure [2]. Consequently, it would appear necessary to develop a rational approach to improve structural reliability of wind turbine blades.

Quantitative studies conducted by the German institutes of Schleswig Holstein (LWK Database) and Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy and Energy System Technology (WMEP Database) have shown similar failure rates downtime of different wind turbine sub-assemblies [3]. A survey conducted by Sandia National Laboratory in USA [4] has found that approximately 7% of all wind turbine blades had to be replaced. Based on personal correspondence with wind turbine blade manufacturers Douglas [4] states that this number may probably be even higher than 7%. The operators have reported the leading causes of failure are manufacturing defects and lightning strikes [4].

The US National renewable energy laboratory (NREL) have estimated that 51% of the turbine blade failures are caused by manufacturing defects, 20% are from lightning strikes, 16% from foreign object impacts and 13% from higher tip deflections resulting in collisions with the tower [5].

Manufacturing defects of wind turbine blades influence fatigue properties of the blade, since defects invariably lead to higher stress concentrations in the structure. This can create more crack initiations and growth of the individual defects during the service life. Adhesive layer failure, ply waviness, delamination, voids/porosity and thickness variation are key defects in wind turbine blades. From these porosity and ply waviness have been identified as the most critical manufacturing defects based on data gathered in an industry survey [6]. In recent years stitched heavy tow glass fabrics have become increasingly popular to manufacture turbine blades. These fabric types are susceptible to generate ply waviness which is a concern to structural fatigue life performance.

The primary objective of this research was to evaluate the effect of ply waviness on residual strength and fatigue life of composite wind turbine blades. The methodology used in this research study can serve as an input to develop a strength degradation model, which has the potential of incorporating the influence of manufacturing defects for composite wind turbine blade design and to develop an improved fatigue life estimation model based on residual strength degradation.

2 Fatigue Life Prediction of Wind Turbine Blades

Design constraints for wind turbine structures fall into either extreme load or fatigue categories.[7] Reference [8] has identified the following design steps for fatigue:

- Determination of wind flow (a Weibull function is used by most studies).
- Calculation, or measurement, of load spectra for different working conditions (load characterizations can be performed either experimentally or analytically).
- Estimation of the developed stress fields.
- Derivation of S-N curves for the specific case of study.
- Application of the linear Miner's rule.
- Employing appropriate multi-axial failure criteria in the case of multi-axial stress states.

One of the most important drawbacks of current fatigue life investigations phenomena is that it is based on a deterministic approach; but the real governing situation is stochastic as a result of random variation of wind pattern. A second drawback is that the current fatigue life estimation methods have not thoroughly considered effects of manufacturing defects and in-service damage for fatigue life prediction of wind turbine blades.

According to [9], in the current design guidelines, lifetime prediction of wind turbine blades is based on the Miner summation. This assumes that fatigue damage, which is estimated from S-N curves, is a linear summation using the following expression [10],

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (1)$$

where N_i is the number of cycles to failure, n_i is the number of cycles present in the fatigue loading indicator, and i is the cycle type (cycle type indicates combination of maximum stress and R ratio). The parameter D is the "damage" parameter and assumed to be equal to "1" at failure [8]. Miner summation has two main drawbacks which lead to poor predictions for fatigue life.

1. The damage parameter "D" has no physical meaning (for stiffness or strength) other than indicating failure; also, it only has a binary value, either "failed" or "intact".
2. Miner's sum does not take into account the sequence of applied stress cycles. That is, for a given set of stress cycles damage con-

tribution for any cycle is independent of the damage state prior to the load cycle.

In most cases, designers use higher safety factors to reduce the influence of potential defects for structural reliability. This increases material consumption, weight and cost of wind turbine blade production. Consequently, it is important to develop fatigue life estimation methodologies that incorporate the influence of manufacturing defects such as ply waviness and crack density for safe fatigue life prediction.

Progressive Damage (Cumulative), Phenomenological (empirical) and Micro-mechanics are the three main categories of fatigue damage modeling. This study discusses a strength degradation model (using progressive damage) to evaluate the effect of ply waviness for the fatigue life of wind turbine blade materials.

2.1 Life prediction using strength degradation

Strength degradation of rotating composite structures (such as rotor blades) under fatigue loading can be described using residual strength analysis. For the residual strength experiments, specimens are subjected to fatigue loading and tested in tension or compression at a series of predefined percentages of nominal fatigue life. When the mechanical properties of the laminate degrade the failure probability, reliability and fatigue life can be determined from the density distribution function for residual strength as shown in Figure 1,

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of statistical distribution of static strength, residual strength and fatigue life [11]

The residual strength degradation based fatigue life estimation approach uses the strength-life-

equal-rank-assumption (SLERA) [12]. SLERA states that strength and life ranks are correlated, i.e. specimens with a high initial static strength will have longer lifetimes than specimens with a low initial static strength. OPTIMAT Blade project [13] has shown that strength degradation models can be used to improve the life prediction methodology by replacing Miner's sum. The Classical Fatigue Analysis (CFA) and Residual Property Analysis (RPA) are schematically shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Schematic of Classical fatigue analysis and Residual strength/stiffness analysis [13]

Residual strength “ S_r ” could be expressed by using the following generic equation [13],

$$S_r = S_0 - (S_0 - S_{max}) \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)^C \quad (2)$$

where:

- S_r = Residual Strength after n cycles at S_{max}
- S_0 = Initial Static Strength
- S_{max} = Maximum load applied in fatigue
- n = Number of cycles with S_{max}
- N = Number of cycles at S_{max} which would lead to failure

A heuristic approach is required to evaluate the parameter “ C ” [14]. The value of the parameter “ C ” has to be found from residual strength tests and Nijssen et.al. [15] have described the required testing conditions for a thorough determination,

- The testing spectrum should cover at least three representative fatigue regimes (tension-tension, compression-compression and tension-compression fatigue)

- The residual strength testing should be carried out at both high cycle and low cycle fatigue.
- The residual strength testing is required to be carried out at different R values.
- It is required to test a sufficient number of specimens at each entry in the test matrix to obtain statistically viable and interpretable results.

Equation (2) is used to evaluate parameter “ C ”. In this context a comprehensive testing program is required to thoroughly evaluate “ C ” and to develop a more improved fatigue life estimation technique. However, one regime of fatigue testing is enough to make early estimations on the effect of manufacturing defects, such as ply waviness, on fatigue failure of wind turbine blades. As lower “ C ” values suggest early failure, the criticality of the defect can be specified by defining a specific value range for “ C ” and finding the distribution of “ C ” under specified defect parameter. For example, if the considered manufacturing defect is ply waviness, it is possible to compare the variation of “ C ” with respect to different A/L ratios where A is the wave height and L is the wavelength. Figure 3 illustrates the different degradation types with reference to value of “ C ”.

Fig. 3: Different degradation types; from left to right: $C < 1$, $C = 1$, and $C > 1$ [13]

3 Experimental

An experimental test program was carried out by manufacturing suitable ‘flat’ and wavy’ laminate specimens from stitched biaxial glass fiber fabrics.

3.1 Specimen geometry

Specimens were based on the DIN EN ISO 527 Part 4 standard which is commonly used for the determination of tensile properties for fiber reinforced plastics. This standard has been chosen because of the simplicity of the specimen geometry and production. The specimen geometry chosen was the Type 2 geometry with the specimen length being 250mm, its width 25mm and thickness between 2 and 3 mm [16]. These specimens have also been used for fatigue tests.

The wavy specimens had the same dimensions of the flat specimen when seen from the top view with a difference of a single wave which can be seen in the side-view. Figure 4 shows the specimen dimensions. The wave amplitude was 1mm and the wavelength 24mm.

Fig. 4 Specimen dimensions

3.2 Specimen Manufacturing

Materials used in specimen manufacturing were a stitched biaxial glass fiber material from the producer SAERTEX and an infiltration resin RIMR235 with RIMR236 hardener from the producer Momentive. In order to achieve good specimen quality the Vacuum Assisted Process (VAP[®]) was used, which ensured a high fibre content with negligible void content. This process is quite similar to Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) in such a way, that the main tools and approach are the same. The only difference between these processes is a special semi-permeable membrane which allows evacuation of air, but stops the resin from flowing out. This enabled an optimal laminate with practically “zero void” content to be produced.

Figure (5-a and 5-b) illustrate this process schematically for the cases of flat and wavy specimens. The laminate preform (2) is placed on top of a tooling (6) which is then, together with the resin inlet (1), enclosed in a semi-permeable membrane (4). This membrane is then, along with the vacuum outlet (7), enclosed in a vacuum bag (5). A vacuum pump is turned on, with the resin inlet closed off in order to apply vacuum under the bag. This vacuum makes the laminate settle firmly onto the tooling with the fibers pressing onto each other to provide a high volume fibre ratio in the laminate. Resin is then introduced through the resin inlet until the fibers are properly saturated.

Fig. 5 VAP[®] specimen production: a) flat plate b) wavy plate

After the fibers have been saturated with resin, the resin intake is closed off and the trapped air voids are vacuumed out through the membrane stopping the resin from overflowing. This results in a

laminates which have an extremely low content of voids because the air evacuation is also happening after the resin inlet has been shut off, thus letting the trapped air pockets and voids to exit the laminate.

For the wavy specimens it was found that only a vacuum bag was not sufficient and the top curvatures were not parallel to the bottom curvatures resulting in a specimen that could not be properly characterized with an A/L ratio. Therefore a top mold part (8) was placed between the membrane and the vacuum bag. This was found to successfully press the laminate from the top and provide a wavy specimen of constant thickness.

Finished plates were put in an oven for 15 hours at 80° C in order to get the best mechanical properties following the manufacturer's recommendations [17]. After the tempering process, end-tabs were bonded to the plates using A10/B10 structural resin from the producer Lange & Ritter and specimens were cut to size with a circular diamond saw.

After production, the wavy specimens were put under a stereo microscope in order to measure their true waviness. Current production process yields a minor error of about 2% in the wave A/L ratio. In future this will have to be improved by improving the mold design.

3.3 Testing Approach

The testing equipment included two testing machines - one 100kN INSTRON 8502 servo-hydraulic testing machine and one 250kN Schenk-Trebel universal testing machine. As additional accessories two mechanical extensometers DD1 from the producer HBM were used in order to measure specimen strains. The extensometers had a maximum $\pm 2,5$ mm blade tip displacement which was found to be sufficient as all the specimens broke before the extensometers reached their limits. The extensometers were set symmetrically on both specimen faces using a quick fixing apparatus. This allowed a mean strain to be determined from the average of the two surface strain measurements.

The evaluation of residual strength of composite laminates was performed by exposing them first to fatigue (at an R-value of 0.1, where R is the Minimum:Maximum stress ratio) up to a certain number of cycles (N) and then applying a quasi-static tensile load to final failure. The testing machine is force

controlled with the maximum stress being set at 25% of the ultimate stress of a flat specimen. This stress has been chosen, because it is below the stress necessary to cause delamination of the wavy specimens. A frequency of 5Hz was used for all fatigue specimens in order to avoid autogenous heating, which commonly takes place with glass reinforced composites subjected to cyclic loading at higher frequencies. A temperature measuring sensor was placed on some of the specimens which showed no significant temperature increase during testing.

Testing starts with the specimen being loaded with a tensile load up to a predetermined "zero amplitude" point and then a sinus function cycling is started with predetermined amplitude. After a certain number of cycles in the fatigue test, the machine automatically sets the load to zero and switches to displacement control in order to avoid any further specimen loading. Following the fatigue tests, specimens were again photographed under a stereo light microscope in order to check for cracks and/or delamination.

The next step was the tensile testing which followed the DIN EN ISO 527-4 standard. All specimens have been tested with a crosshead speed of 2mm/min. In order to identify the type of failure and to determine the point of delamination, a USB camera microscope was used. Figure 6 illustrates the tensile test setup.

Fig. 6 Tensile test setup

The tensile load at which a laminate fails is defined as the residual strength of the laminate at N number of cycles. Residual strength tests were per-

formed at various points of expected life time. Table 1 summarizes results from the test program.

Table 1 Wavy specimen tensile test results

Specimen	Ultimate Stress[MPa]	Cycles
1-W-1	329,9	0
1-W-7	396,9	0
1-W-4	361,6	0
1-W-9	328,7	0
1-W-10	361,5	0
1-W-2	302,8	50000
1-W-8	247,4	50000
1-W-6	262,1	100000
1-W-17	337,6	100000
1-W-11	293,7	200000
1-W-3	243,8	250000
1-W-5	347,9	250000
1-W-16	303,7	250000
1-W-12	299,1	300000
1-W-18	292,4	400000
1-W-19	315,5	400000
1-W-13	353,11	400000
1-W-14	311,4	450000
1-W-21	322	600000
1-W-20	334,8	800000

4 FEM Analysis

Finite element analyses were carried out using the commercial code PAM-CRASH from ESI Group [18] and FEM models were developed specifically to simulate delamination mechanisms.

A stacked shell approach has been chosen in order to minimize processing times. Each ply was represented by shell elements of 0,25mm in size using an elastic orthotropic composite model, Type 131. The plies were connected using a dedicated delamination model, Type 303, which allowed for failure and delamination crack growth. Figure 7 depicts the numerical model.

Figure 8 shows a comparison of test and numerical model results for the non-fatigued wavy specimen loaded quasi statically to failure. Added to this comparison experimental results from a quasi-static tensile test of a specimen that has been subjected to fatigue are shown. The numerical analysis curve

compares well to a quasi-static tensile test of a non-fatigued specimen. Both curves show a rapid decrease in slope at a similar load level. The specimen flattens rapidly as the displacement of the crossheads continues causing a drop in the loading. After the specimen has flattened the slope of the curve in-

Fig. 7 Numerical model of a wavy specimen

creases and stays almost constant until the ultimate load and specimen failure. Video recordings of quasi-static test indicate that the point in time where the crack forms and the delamination is initiated corresponds to the point where the slope of the curve decreases. From this figure it is easy to see that the slope of the numerical analysis curve returns to the initial value and the slope of the non-fatigued experimental curve is lower than the initial one. Due to matrix cracking in the 90° plies of the whole specimen the stiffness of the overall laminate decreases. These effects still need to be included in the simulation in order to calibrate the specimen.

Fig. 8 Overlay comparison of a simulation with experiments (Force kN vs. gauge displacement mm)

The fatigued specimen undergoes a different failure mechanism and the experimental results curve is different. The slope of the curve increases gradually as the wave flattens. This kind of behavior can be explained with the delamination that already occurred during fatigue tests of the specimens. The energy accumulation needed in order for the cracks to form does not accumulate, and the plies slide on

top of each other allowing the wave to straighten itself gradually as the load increases. A numerical model that could simulate a fatigued specimen is currently under development in further research.

5 Results Summary

5.1 Fatigue testing- Failure Mechanism

During the fatigue test, matrix micro-cracking starts developing transversely to the loading direction along the entire specimen. As the test progresses larger cracks are detectable. It has been determined that large cracks develop first in the middle of the wave in 80% of the wavy specimens.

Starter cracks usually occur in the fiber-matrix interface or in the 90° fiber bundles themselves causing them to split. It has also been recorded that with increase in the number of cycles these cracks grow along the fibers and between the fiber-matrix interfaces leading to ply delamination and separation. It has not been observed that the stitching stops crack development, or that delamination happens more often between plies which are not stitched together. Figure 9 shows a specimen that has been loaded with 100000 cycles in which cracks have developed into the middle of the specimen.

Figure 9 Wavy specimen after 100000 loading cycles with cracks in the middle of the wave zoomed

During the fatigue tests the cracks spread throughout the wavy part of the specimen weakening the matrix. This allows the specimen to straighten easier than a specimen that was not subjected to fatigue loading. This can be confirmed from the decrease in strength of specimens that have undergone a large number of fatigue cycles.

The flat and wavy specimens undergo different failure mechanisms. Flat specimens failed under

fiber failure whereas wavy specimen failure was dominated by delamination as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 a) Failure of flat specimen (fiber rupture) and b) wavy specimen (delamination dominated)

5.2 Data Analysis

The strength degradation data for flat specimens follow a more linear residual strength degradation when compared to the one wave specimens. One wave specimen residual strength shows early reduction at the starting point, then remains fairly constant, with even a small increase in strength in a range of up to 30% -80% of their total fatigue life; thereafter and a rapid drop is seen up to final failure.

The limited experimental data of this study suggests the parameter “C” for wavy specimens varies with the number of cycles. Figure 11 shows the results for the factor “C” for both flat and wavy specimens calculated analytically from equation 3. Flat specimens are represented with blue dots, and wavy specimens with red dots.

Fig. 11 C values vs life fraction

In the authors' opinion a suitable model to fit this data would be the "OM model" [14] which has proposed factor "C" to be a function of the number of cycles.

$$S_r = S_0 - (S_0 - S_{max}) \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)^C \quad (3)$$

$$C = f\left(\frac{n}{N}\right) = (k_1 \exp\left(k_2 \frac{n}{N}\right)) \quad (4)$$

By fitting this function to the data using the method proposed in [14] one can see that the curve reasonably represents the experimental data acquired.

Figure 12 shows the residual strength data. The purple dots denote the residual strength results of the wavy specimens, and blue dots the residual strength results of flat specimens. The authors believe it may be possible to use residual strength degradation modeling to evaluate the effect of ply waviness with different A/L ratio of ply waviness. This will require additional testing in order to gain more data for the numerical model; this is currently being undertaken in further research.

6 Major Conclusions

The combined static fatigue progressive failure analysis has the ability to recognize which damage modes are responsible for reduction of residual strength as well as which of them causes final failure of the laminates. Consequently, residual strength degradation based fatigue life estimation model provides opportunity for analysing the influence of manufacturing defects such as ply waviness and crack density for the fatigue life of composite wind turbine blades. This is advantageous compared to the traditional Miner summation rule.

Residual strength data were collected for tension-tension fatigue (R=0.1). In this analysis it has been identified that fiber waviness induced delamination noticeably reduces residual strength of glass fibre laminate in the first 10-15% lifetime fraction and also shows sudden-death type residual strength degradation. Because of this combined "wear in – sudden death" behaviour, the OM model should be used to correctly display this behaviour. If the stress

Fig. 12 Residual strength curves for wavy (full) and flat (dashed)

overcomes the delamination point, the lifetime of wavy specimens decreases significantly.

Ongoing research will focus on residual strength after compression-compression as well as tension-compression fatigue. The interaction between stress level and fatigue regimes will also be investigated by submitting specimens to block-loading tests and to simple load spectra.

References

- [1] CompositesWorld.com. (June 1, 2008). "Suzlon Blade Recall: Retrofit Program to Address Cracking" June.1.2009. <http://www.compositesworld.com/news/suzlon-blade-recall-retrofit-program-to-address-cracking.aspx>. [Accessed December 30, 2011].
- [2] Caithness Wind Farm Information Forum "Summary of Wind Turbine Accident data to 30 Sept 2012". <http://www.caithnesswindfarms.co.uk/page4.htm> [Accessed: 10th November 2012].
- [3] S. Faulstich, B. Hahn "Comparison of different wind turbine concepts due to their effects on reliability". UpWind, EU supported project nr. 019945(SES6), deliverable WP7.3.2, public report, Kassel, 2009
- [4] D. S. Cairns, T. Riddle, J. Nelson. "Wind turbine composite blade manufacturing: the need for understanding defect origins, prevalence, implications and reliability". Reportsand2011-1094, 2011.
- [5] NENUPHAR. "Wind farms designed for the off-shore environment". Workshop, June 2010,
- [6] J. W. Nelson, T. W. Riddle, and D. S. Cairns. "Effects of defects in composite wind turbine blades: round 1 sandia report" Sand2012-8110, 2012. <http://prod.sandia.gov/techlib/access-control.cgi/2012/128110.pdf> [Accessed: 12th December 2012].

- [7] M. M. Shokrieh, R. Rafiee “*Simulation of fatigue failure in a full composite wind turbine blade*”, *Composite Structures*, 74, pp332-342, 2006
- [8] A. P. Vassilopoulos (ed). “*Fatigue life prediction of composites and composite structures*”. Woodhead publishing, 2010, pp506.
- [9] R.P.L. Nijssen, D., D. Samborsky, J.F.Mandell, and D.R.V. van Delft. “*Fatigue and residual strength degradation in wind turbine rotor blade composites*”. Online At [Http://Www.Docstoc.Com](http://www.docstoc.com), [Accessed: 10th November 2012].
- [10] M.A. Miner “*Cumulative Damage in Fatigue*”, presented at meeting of Aviation Division, 1945 (june 16-17), pp. A159-A164
- [11] B. Harris “*Fatigue in composites, Science and technology of the, fatigue response of fibre-reinforced plastics*” Woodhead publishing, 2013.
- [12] P.C: Chou, R. Croman “*Residual Strength in Fatigue Based on the Strength-Life Equal Rank Assumption*” *Composite Materials*, Vol. 12, pp. 177-194, 1978
- [13] R.P.L. Nijssen, A. van Wingerde “*Residual Strength Tests data and analysis*”. OPTIMAT Project, doc.no.10285, 2006.
- [14] R.P.L. Nijssen. “*Fatigue Life Prediction and Strength Degradation Of Wind Turbine Rotor Blade Composites*”, SAND2006-7810P, 2007.
- [15] T. Philippidis, V. Passipoularidis “*Residual strength after fatigue in composites: Theory vs. experiment*”, *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 29, Issue 12, pp. 2104-2116, 2007
- [16] DIN EN ISO 527 *Plastics - Determination of tensile properties*, ISO 527, 1997
- [17] Momentive, “*EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS® RIMR 235 and EPIKURE™ Curing Agent RIMH 235-238*” Technical Data sheet, 2006
- [18] ESI Group, “*Virtual Performance solution 2012 – solver reference manual*”, 2012